

Ukrainian as a foreign language: practical types of class work

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The main feature of language material is that its assimilation doesn't remain at the perception level and needs realization in the corresponding skills which are reached by training. The didactic essence of exercises method is that the teacher by means of special tasks, performed by foreign students, directs them to language skills

development. Therefore, it is necessary to take exercises of Ukrainian as foreign language mean performance of educational tasks by students to study theoretical material and mastering practical skills.

It is important for a technique of teaching Ukrainian as a foreign language to study the most rational system of training exercises. Exercises are classified, proceeding from different criteria: contents (according to the educational program), forms of performance (oral and written), complexity degrees etc. Ukrainian as a foreign language is provided the introduction of practical tasks and exercises systems created by reference to specific perception features by foreign students of non-mother tongue.

The analysis of works of teaching experts methodology concerning the technique of teaching Ukrainian as a foreign language, it is necessary to define that there are different types of exercises classification, for example: according to the nature of performed actions, educational purpose, relation to the source text, according to the place of speaking skills formation, according to linguistic contents, in a speaking form, according to quantity of tasks to language material. It is determined in methodical materials that "organizing study of a training material and creating the exercises system, the teacher should be guided by their role in the course of enrichment and improvement of foreign students speech" [2, p. 29]. Practically the most expedient is the opposition to the types of work which are performed on ready material and improvisations. The exercises of the first group provide: observation and the analysis of language units in the text; designing of different language units (according to the models, schemes). The second group consists of exercises devoted to the designing of coherent texts (creative works) and editing of own statements [1]. Besides, formation of speaking skills to pass the following stages: perception and reproductive reconstruction of language means; formation of abilities to create and apply language means; formation of abilities to choose the necessary language material for expression of a certain contents; use of the acquired language material in unprepared statements [2, p. 104]. Each of the noted stages is accompanied by the performance of a certain type of exercises: analytical (qualification and selective),

transformational, constructive and communicative. Only when each of the performed works plays the own the role in the formation of a certain communicative ability then all exercises are purposeful, the next is connected with previous and help foreign students on the new level of language acquisition. They make the complete system, which is one of the most important prerequisites of successful study.

Also, it is necessary to mention that rather effective exercise is the so-called “commenting letter” which was often used 15-20 years ago in the course of study Russian as foreign language, however subsequently it has been forced by different methodical innovations. Meanwhile, the value of “commenting letter” which promotes the development of writing abilities and skills is incontestable. In a point of fact it is a kind of a precautionary dictation, however, it is carried out more vigorously, at fast speed (that, certainly, is more economical). The teacher dictates students separate words, word-combinations or sentences. One of the students (commentator) explains the spelling of words, use of punctuations sign and grammatical rules without stop writing. If the foreign student will have some complications and he will keep silence, the teacher calls surnames of two-three stronger students who have to continue to comment or calls someone during his commenting to help or to correct him.

Unfortunately, this exercise is rarely practiced in HEI because of lack of experience of many teachers inappropriate application of the language analysis and the effective methodical help of scientists.

Therefore exercises and tasks of Ukrainian as a foreign language is a component in assimilation and improvement of knowledge, in the development of skills. Choosing exercises, it is necessary to consider not only the content of the studied material but also character and a form of tasks performance (oral, written), connections of exercises, the sequence according to the degree of difficulty (from simple to difficult). At the same time, it is very important to choose such exercise which would allow providing practical application of the got theoretical knowledge. Work on their assimilation should be finished with speech or conversational practice.

It should be mentioned that it is inopportune to overload foreign students with the excess quantity of practical tasks and exercises which, undoubtedly, should be optimum. Instructing to the performance of the exercise should be accompanied by the caution of possible difficulties and typical mistakes which students could meet in the course of task performance.

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